

CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF *RIP VAN WINKLE* BY WASHINGTON IRVING WASHINGTON IRVING'İN *RIP VAN WINKLE* ÖYKÜSÜ ÜZERİNE ELEŞTİREL ÇÖZÜMLEME

Kübra YÖRÜK

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Abstract

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is an interdisciplinary method focused on analyzing ideologies and power dynamics, whether explicit or implicit, within discourses. Its interdisciplinary nature stems from its collaboration with fields such as Rhetoric, Text linguistics, Anthropology, Philosophy, Socio-Psychology, Cognitive Science, Literary Studies and Sociolinguistics, as well as Applied Linguistics and Pragmatics. It is a method used in the analysis of both written and spoken discourses. It enables the identification of social inequalities, power abuse, and ideological elements that emerge in discourse. It is also used to make sense of social media, advertising, or politics discourses based on how the manipulations that occur through discourse in daily life shape individuals or societies. Washington Irving's *Rip Van Winkle* that is the subject of the study, is considered one of the first works of American literature. Based on the premise that discourses only reveal their true meaning when considered within the context in which they are produced, this work, written in 1819, requires evaluation within its historical context. While Irving's work was once interpreted as a legendary escape from history, it is now considered an important part of American history. This study aims to examine *Rip Van Winkle* narrative within the framework of Critical Discourse Analysis, to shed light on issues such as the socio-political structure of the period and the balances of power in its historical background, while also reaching historical information about America at the time.

Keywords: Critical Discourse Analysis, Power, National Identity, American Society, *Rip Van Winkle*, Washington Irving.

Özet

Eleştirel Söylem Çözümlemesi (EŞÇ) söylemlerde gizli ya da açık olarak ortaya konmuş ideolojileri, güç dengelerini analiz etmeye odaklanmış disiplinler arası bir yöntemdir. Retorik, Metindilbilim, Antropoloji, Felsefe, Sosyo-Psikoloji, Bilişsel Bilim, Edebiyat Çalışmaları ve Toplumdilbilimin yanı sıra Uygulamalı Dilbilim ve Pragmatik gibi alanlarla iş birliği içinde olması sebebiyle disiplinler arası bir çalışma alanı pozisyonundadır. Hem yazılı hem de sözlü söylemlerin çözümlenmesinde kullanılan bir yöntemdir. Söylemde ortaya çıkan toplumsal eşitsizlikler, güç istismarı ve ideolojik unsurlar gibi durumların tespitini sağlar. Günlük yaşantıda söylemle ortaya çıkan manipülasyonların bireyleri ya da toplumları nasıl şekillendirdiğine dayanarak sosyal-medya, reklam, ya da politika söylemlerini anlamlandırmada da kullanılır. Çalışmaya konu olan Washington Irving'in *Rip Van Winkle*'i Amerikan edebiyatının ilk eserlerinden biri olarak kabul edilmektedir. Söylemlerin gerçek anlamlarını ancak üretildikleri bağlam içinde ele alındığında ortaya koydukları gerçeğinden hareketle, 1819'da yazılan bu eser tarihsel bağlamı içinde değerlendirilmeyi gerektirir. Irving'in bu eseri, bir zamanlar tarihten efsanevi bir kaçış olarak okunurken, günümüzde Amerika tarihinin önemli bir parçası olarak kabul edilir. Bu çalışma, *Rip Van Winkle* anlatısını Eleştirel Söylem Çözümlemesi çerçevesinde ele alarak, dönemin sosyo-politik yapısı, tarihsel arka planındaki güç dengeleri gibi konulara geniş anlamda açıklık getirmeyi amaçlarken dönemin Amerika'sı hakkında tarihsel bilgilere ulaşmayı amaçlar.

Anahtar kelimeler: Eleştirel Söylem Çözümlemesi, Güç, Ulusal Kimlik, Amerikan Toplumunu, *Rip Van Winkle*, Washington Irving.

Introduction

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a research discipline that uncovers power dynamics, ideologies, and social norms in language. “It is a discourse analytical method that primarily studies the way social-power abuse and inequality are enacted, reproduced, legitimated, and resisted by text and talk in the social and political context” (van Dijk, 2015). CDA analyses the way in which socio-political and ideological contexts influence individuals or society through written or spoken discourses. Ideology is a set of ideas that determine the social, economic, political and moral values of a society and, therefore, its view of the world, based on different systems. “(...) ideologies were forms of 'false consciousness', that is, popular but misguided beliefs inculcated by the ruling class in order to legitimate the status quo, and to conceal the real socioeconomic conditions of the workers.” (Dijk, 2000) CDA seeks to explain the power relations of language and the way it is used in social contexts. Leading researchers such as Teun A. van Dijk argue that it is a field in which power structures are reproduced. “A literary work is one of the human-specific communicative forms. While literary texts representing a fictional world, they bore the traces of the real sociocultural world surrounding them.” (Torusdağ, 2018). Literary texts are windows that open onto the real world. Their fictional content and aesthetic attitudes do not separate them from the real world. They are open or closed expressions of social norms, traditions, power relations and ideological structures. These literary discourses serve not only as a source of information about the period for the reader, but also as a research resource for the critical discourse analyst.

Washington Irving was born the youngest child of a merchant family from New York. “No writer was as successful as Irving at humanizing the land, endowing it with a name and a face and a set of legends. The story of *Rip Van Winkle*, who slept for 20 years, waking to find the colonies had become independent, eventually became folklore.” (Vanspanckeren, 1994). Adaptations were made in various fields such as cinema, theatre and began to be accepted as an American myth. The life of the man who returned after 20 years refers to the reconstruction of the American nation and includes the spirit of the nation. As an allegorical short story, *Rip Van Winkle* symbolizes an American awakening. *Rip Van Winkle*, with its historical context and rich metaphors, has become a work that touches on social, cultural and, above all, political issues before and after the American Reformation. It draws attention to American consciousness with its historical context and ideological deep structure. It bridges the

relationships between society and the individual through history and nature with the Kaatskill Mountains.

Washington Irving, one of the pioneers of the American Romanticists, highlights American identity in his work. He raises the American voice and does not back off from describing how America was different from Europe and especially from England, as well as its nature and landscape. His short story *Rip Van Winkle* reflects the American transformations and historical background. With its ideological essentials and metaphorical elements, Washington Irving demonstrates American identity and social change.

The aim of this study is to show how ideology, power dynamics and historical context are deeply intertwined in the story by examining Irving's epic folklore work through the method of Critical Discourse Analysis.

Rip Van Winkle

Before America was discovered, it was believed to be the Promised Land that was in dreams, sacred in the Bible. With its discovery, countries such as England both wanted to send the people who disturbed the peace in their homelands and to achieve prosperity in their own countries, and they were curious and wanted to settle and develop new trade networks. The magic of the discovered New World was very great. "Throughout the contemporary era, the peoples that eventually made up the numerous Native American ethno linguistic and nationalist groups developed gradually." (Grant, 2012). Colonial activities to explore and dominate the continent continued with the British, French, Germans, Dutch, and Spanish. "The enormous size of the continent naturally led to the development of a wide variety of settlements, cultures and peoples. This occurred as a result of trade, travel and, inevitably, war" (Grant, 2012). The New York area was settled by the Dutch. They called it New Netherland. They planned the city according to today's New York city plan. Their trade activities enabled them to establish political and commercial relations with the local people. The attacks on the strategic areas of the Netherlands by the British caused them to leave the region. The name of New Netherlands, which was taken over by the British, was changed to New York. This conflict between the Netherlands and England was a show of power for England. "This renewed interest in New Netherland history provides a welcome contribution to the often Anglo-centred narrative of early American history. But as historians highlight the Dutch colonial past, the enslaved population often receives only marginal attention." (Maika et al., 2014) The fact that the Netherlands was present there despite its defeat in American history shows that its influence

continues even today. Dutch traditions, social norms and cultural schema have been integrated into American culture.

Although the story of *Rip Van Winkle* is associated with an American society that has achieved independence, its historical context is much more twisted. The main character Rip is the story of a lazy man living in a village near the Kaatskil Mountains. “One of the most celebrated characters in American fiction is *Rip Van Winkle*, the name of one of the Dutch colonists of New York, whose adventures are related in Washington Irving’s “Sketch Book.”” (*Rip Van Winkle’s Return*, 1879). *Rip Van Winkle* is one of the first important works of folklore in American literature. It is reminded that New York was once a Dutch colony. It is based on the American conflict between the old and the new during the independence process. Washington Irving, one of the leading figures of the American Romantic movement, has brought a myth to his country. He created a local folklore with the cultures and traditions of the Dutch and created a global echo by writing it down.

The story of *Rip Van Winkle*, one of the key figures of American mythology, begins with historical records. “[The following Tale was found among the papers of the late Diedrich Knickerbocker, an old gentleman of New York, who was very curious in the Dutch history of the province, and the manners of the descendants from its primitive settlers.” (Irving, 1988). In the first lines, an imaginary Dutch historian named Diedrich Knickerbocker takes on the role of narrator. In this way, the reader’s trust is gained and the feeling of objectivity is given as if there is a historical reality. On the other hand, it is also seen that the roots of American history are based on Europeans. In terms of critical discourse, it is observed that there is ‘reproduction’ in the cultural context. Although it is a fictional story, it holds the power element as if it were serving a realistic history. This in turn serves an ideology that explains how in American nation-building illegitimate activities were legitimised and colonisation and massacres continued. Dutch nostalgia is romanticized by the Dutch historian character, but the concepts of a nation and independence in the following lines are proof that this book actually refers to the American consciousness.

“In place of these, a lean, bilious-looking fellow, with his pockets full of handbills, was haranguing vehemently about rights of citizens, elections, members of Congress, liberty, Bunker’s hill, heroes of seventy-six, and other words, which were a perfect Babylonish jargon to the bewildered Van Winkle.” (Irving, 1988).

Despite the European nostalgia in the first lines of the book, the American Revolution forms an ideological basis. First, when considered in terms of Critical Discourse Analysis, ideological expressions such as congress, liberty, and election do not appeal to every segment of society. It is shown that independence, while putting the old order behind it, causes inner turmoil. The character Rip missed the American Revolution by sleeping for 20 years. His awakening signifies the birth of the new order. Being responsible with the old order is associated with lazy individuals having political consciousness in the new order. Old and new, past and future are compared. “Irving did not share the restless energy of the typical American. Unlike most of his countrymen he seems to have found more to interest him in the past than in the present or future. Janus-like, his face was set both toward the east and toward the west. However, Irving's inclination to the east with its Old World traditions, some think, made his love for the west kick the beam. It is true he found in the historic personages and romantic traditions of the past the chief sources of his inspiration.” (Bowen, 1906).

The new order manipulates the public with various discourses. The public, who cannot fully understand what the discourses mean, is manipulated and a propaganda is carried out. It is proof that discourses create national consciousness by uniting individuals. The character Rip is stuck in both the old order and the new order. His passive, lazy state has led him to loneliness and even sleep in both orders. A study says; Tieman De Vries, a distinguished Dutch historian, stated that Washington Irving's portrayal of the Dutch people as stupid and lazy in *Rip Van Winkle* was a kind of smear campaign. He claimed that it was not the original *Rip Van Winkle* story (Young, 1960). As stated in the story Irving may have underestimated the Netherlands. He may have shown laziness and humiliation, but it is the American nation that takes power. It is the power show of America, which won the struggle for independence and formed its own identity. By marginalising the Netherlands, he showed his own superiority in the lines. It blended the culture inherited from the Netherlands with its own power elements. The American nation includes a strong, democratic and modern structure. Power dynamics and dominance are in the hands of America to the same extent.

“God knows,” exclaimed he, at his wit’s end; “I’m not myself—I’m somebody else—that’s me yonder—no—that’s somebody else got into my shoes—I was myself last night, but I fell asleep on the mountain, and they’ve changed my gun, and every thing’s changed, and I’m changed, and I can’t tell what’s my name, or who I am!” (Irving, 1988).

Rip's sleeping and disappearance for 20 years shows his identity conflict and inability to establish social balance. Rip, who fell asleep during the period of British oppression, which is thought to be represented by his wife, woke up to the independence of America. When Rip woke up; there was a revolution in America. The social order and political ideas had changed. Rip, who could not find his friends, his wife and children, was not only in individual disappearance, but also represents the confusion of the transition from the old order, monarchy, and oppression to the new order, democracy. As in the expression "I'm not myself", the character is unable to determine his position in society. The identity crisis shows that the character accepts the society as an element of power. It expresses the situation that rejects the monarchy regime and oppression and at the same time has difficulty in adapting to the new. Whereas the old order was based on laziness, the new order wants people to take an active role in politics and government. This situation shows that individuals like Rip, who are used to being lazy, strengthen their balance with the element of power. Rip is a serious representation of social and individual transformations and in-betweens. The story is a strong discourse in which cultural, political, and historical contexts are reflected.

Rip's wife is an important representation of gender roles, power balances, and ideologies. Mengeling (1964) states that Dame Van Winkle remains one of the truly great caricatures in all of fiction, and it is only right that she be drawn along such lines, for she represents much more than simply a shrewish wife with broomstick in hand. She is a caricature of all those unpleasant pressures which depreciate and lash out at the unpractical and the imaginative.

His wife's nagging about Rip's laziness and irresponsibility is not only an individual rebellion but also a reflection of social ideologies. His wife says that in the patriarchal order, her husband is not fulfilling his responsibilities in the family and that although the economic obligations lie with the man, he is not of that character. "If left to himself, he would have whistled life away in perfect contentment; but his wife kept continually dinning in his ears about his idleness, his carelessness, and the ruin he was bringing on his family." (Irving, 1988). His wife's regular complaining is not only an individual character trait but also a critical approach against social ideologies. A woman cleans, cooks, and raises children at home, while a man's duty in society is to make economic opportunities prosperous. While Rip's wife maintains a passive position in society, on the other hand, she wants to bring her husband, who is not responsible, into the social model. It is possible to see whether the patriarchal family model is correct or not, and how much pressure is put on men by restricting women to staying at home

and cooking. While society encourages women to stay at home and take on domestic responsibilities, the man's only duty is to provide financial opportunities for his wife to fulfil these responsibilities. Rip's wife is the critical point of view of the restriction of the roles given to men and women in the patriarchal society. Although she wants to see Rip as a responsible husband, Rip's failure to satisfy his wife pulls him away and makes him escape. Even the death of his wife does not provide Rip with relief at some point. "Even though his wife is long gone and buried, Rip can only squeeze a "drop of comfort" from this intelligence, for the forces which she represented now reign supreme. Rip is more a misfit than ever before." (Mengeling, 1964). Another point of view here; Dame Van Winkle is England, which is a repressive regime. Even when America took its independence, there is a situation in which England aroused fear on the people.

"I am a poor quiet man, a native of the place, and a loyal subject of the king, God bless him!" Here a general shout burst from the bystanders— "A tory! a tory! a spy! a refugee! hustle him! away with him!" (Irving, 1988).

Dame Van Winkle, like England, left the political scene of America and was replaced by American independence. But Rip could not adapt to any situation and thus became the expression of non-belonging.

Rip who hears strange noises and then sees strange strangers, folklores the story. His disappearance for 20 years is similar to the Odyssey. "One could say of Irving what Longinus said of Homer: his wanderings in a world of "poetic associations" allowed him to fulfil his wish to give America its own mythology in the story of *Rip Van Winkle*." (Staley, 2012). The Kaatskil Mountains are a rumour of mystical power in the story. Kaatskil Mountain exhibits the physical transformation of the character. His mental transformation reveals a character that does not belong. In this way, with mythological elements, Washington Irving gave the American nation a myth that it did not have. Rip, who wants to get away from his wife's critical discourses, is looking for a way out. His escape from reality is symbolized by factors such as the mountain, strange creatures, and alcohol. Like Odyssey, his disappearance for 20 years gave an element of myth. The difference from the Odyssey is that Rip is not a hero. He did not fight with bad guys; he was not in the underworld. Rip just slept. As Staley (2012) indicated, Rip Van Winkle is in part Irving's fantasy of what it might be like to be an Odysseus, returning home with tales of his adventures and thus becoming a hero. Rip's story is exactly the kind of fantasy that Irving would have entertained, as the 'degenerate' proves his worth through the stories he has to tell about his twenty years of 'adventure'.

Irving explains how individuals are affected by social, political, economic, and cultural events with mythical elements. He makes it questionable who has the power, manipulative approaches, and the direction of ideologies through a lazy man. *Rip Van Winkle* offers a look at the social, ideological and cultural elements of Washington Irving, the transformations of American identity and the elements of power. It has a permanent place in American literature with its caricatured, mythical, and folkloric content. “As a matter of fact, there is considerable craft in Irving’s constant juxtaposition of the fantastic and the real in *Rip Van Winkle*.” (Ferguson, 2005). The perspective against gender roles and power dynamics offers social criticism. The nostalgic approach of the past and the democratic footsteps of the future are written with a fantastic journey. Thus, according to Critical Discourse Analysis, the work is not only a story or a folklore text, but also presents a narrative of ideologies and power structures on social norms.

Conclusion

Critical Discourse Analysis is the analysis of the linguistic structures in any discourse and it reveals these analyses by working together with various disciplines. With Şah’s expressions, it examines the ways in which social problems, power and hegemony are reproduced through linguistic, visual and physical expressions. Concepts such as power, inequality and hegemony bring discourse structures to light and provide a broad analysis of the functioning of social structures. In this way, the ideological roles of texts, speeches and visual content are discussed, and thus, not only individual but also social inequalities and injustices are revealed (Şah, 2020).

The analysis of power relations within social structures can be understood through the examination of discourse. Ideological functions affect individuals and society. As Torusdağ (2023) expressed, discourse can shape social structure as it wishes, as a social practice. Its power to shape the social structure brings to mind its manipulative side. Manipulation is a social phenomenon, especially as it involves interacting with and abusing power between groups and social actors. Since it always refers to the manipulation of the minds of the participants, manipulation is a cognitive phenomenon.

Washington Irving conveyed how individual and social dynamics have transformed with interesting folkloric figures like a children’s book with his work *Rip Van Winkle*. He caricatured the individual and social relations. Critical analysis expresses how socio-cultural and historical contexts emerge from power dynamics, ideological activities, and gender roles.

Mengeling (1964) states that in essence, Irving makes brilliant use of two methods of characterization in Rip. The primary method is to show Rip in his different relationships to the scene and to the other people in the story. The other characters, especially Rip's wicked lady, are drawn in caricature. The characters in question are represented by a single significant physical or mental trait, which enables them to reflect on the character and actions of Rip without detracting from the psychological turmoil experienced by the eponymous character.

Rip cannot keep up with the old and new order in society. He is trapped in a lack of belonging. He indicates the manipulative and ideological aspects of society with Dame Van Winkle. The historical, ideological and manipulative background that includes Rip creates consciousness about individual and collective identity about America. *Rip Van Winkle* is not only the mythical story of the lazy individual, but also an examination of the transformation of American consciousness, which contains the element of political and ideological power. Washington Irving brought together the historical context and mythological elements and created harmony. He achieved a permanent position in American literature by creating an American consciousness.

References

- van Dijk, T. A. (2015). Critical discourse analysis. In D. Tannen, H. E. Hamilton, & D. Schiffrin (Ed.), *The handbook of discourse analysis*. (pp. 466-485). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Bowen, E. W. (1906). Washington Irving's place in American literature. *The sewanee review*. 14(2). The Johns Hopkins University Press. 171-183.
- Ferguson, R. A. (2005). *Rip Van Winkle* and the Generational Divide in American Culture. *Early American Literature*, 40(3), 529-544.
- Grant, S. M. (2012). *A concise history of United States of America*. Cambridge University Press.
- Irving, W. (1988). *Rip Van Winkle*. Penguin Books.
- Maika, D. J., Meuwese, M., Mosterman, A. C., Romney, S. S., Noorlander, D. L., Cantwell, A. M., & Wall, Z. d. (2014). Roundtable: The Past, Present and Future of New Netherland Studies. *New York History*. 95(3), 446-490.
- Mengeling, M. E. (1964). Characterization in "*Rip Van Winkle*". *The English journal*, 53(9), 643-646.
- Rip Van Winkle's Return*. (1879). *The Aldine-The Art Journal Of America*, 9(12). 374-377.
- Staley, G. A. (2012). *Rip Van Winkle's "Odyssey"*. *Greece & Rome*, 59(1), 90-103.
- Şah, U. (2020). Eleştirel söylem analizi: Temel yaklaşımlar. *Kültür araştırmaları dergisi*. 1(7), (s. 210-231).
- Torusdağ, G. (2018). Textlinguistic analysis of the short stories and language teaching, sample of Eveline by Joyce. *Dil ve edebiyat araştırmaları*, 18(18), (s. 127-167).

- Torusdağ, G. (2023). Critical analysis on advertising discourses. *RumeliDE dil ve edebiyat arařtırmaları dergisi*, 1(291). (s. 285-292).
- van Dijk, T. A. (2012). *Ideology and discourse a multidisciplinary introduction*. Pompeu Fabra University, Barcelona.
- Vanspankeren, K. (1994). *Outline of American literature*. Paul Malamud, Kathleen Hug, Joann Stern (Ed.). U.S. Department of State, Bureau of International Information Programs.
- Young, P. (1960). Fallen from Time: The Mythic Rip Van Winkle. *The Kenyon Review*, 22(4). (s. 547-573).